

Systems for Wind Monitoring on Black Sea Offshore

1st Andrei Scupi
Faculty of Naval Electromechanics
Constanta Maritime University
Constanta, Romania
andrei.scupi@cmu-edu.eu

2nd Fanel-Viorel Panaitescu
Faculty of Naval Electromechanics
Constanta Maritime University
Constanta, Romania
viorel.panaitescu@cmu-edu.eu

3rd Mariana Panaitescu
Faculty of Naval Electromechanics
Constanta Maritime University
Constanta, Romania
mariana.panaitescu@cmu-edu.eu

4th Ionut Voicu
Faculty of Naval Electromechanics
Constanta Maritime University
Constanta, Romania
ionut.voicu@cmu-edu.eu

5th Catalin Faitar
Faculty of Naval Electromechanics
Constanta Maritime University
Constanta, Romania
catalin.faitar@cmu-edu.eu

6th Nikolay Zlatev
Petroceltic, Varna, Bulgaria
nikolay.zlatev@petroceltic.bg

Abstract—In this paper we gathered specific information about wind characteristics with the help of Vaisala equipment – Wind Cube. The equipment is mounted at top of platform and measure the wind velocity and wind direction multiple times a day for more than half a year, for 20 levels of altitudes. Data collected represents the premises for designing the main characteristics of the wind turbine and its buoy.

Keywords—monitoring systems, Black Sea, WindCube, wind turbine

I. INTRODUCTION

Increasing pollution on the planet motivated the engineering industry to modify and adapt itself to new technology for electricity production. Black Sea is considered a region of medium potential for harnessing wind potential with offshore turbines. The offshore wind turbine is a clean, cost-effective and scalable source of energy, and floating offshore wind energy is expected to play a key role in unlocking the potential of offshore area.

The exploitation of wind turbines in the area far from the shore, at more than 20 Nm. In this area, the water depth is over 40 m and therefore the solution for mounting the wind turbines cannot be the one fixed in the seabed, but using an semi-ballasted floating platform. The solution is adapted to the western area of the Black Sea, where the wind potential is medium, and therefore the construction is special [1].

To monitor and record the values for wind velocity and direction a Wind Cube from Vaisala was bought and mounted on an oil rig platform Galata, Bugaria.

Galata platform (Fig. 1) is a fixed, earth gas production platform, owned and operated by a private gas company Melrose Resources Sarl. The platform is located in western part of the Black Sea on the Bulgarian shelf platform (34 m depth) 26 km east from the city of Varna [2]. The geographical position of Galata platform are 43.044595 Latitude and 28.193250 Longitude.

On top of the platform at 23.5 m above sea water level the Windcube was mounted (Fig. 2). WindCube for offshore has been engineered with a robust casing for integration into floating buoys and other harsh offshore locations, such as lighthouses, substations, and vessels. A mobile Lidar collecting continuously 300 meters wind profile data over

20 simultaneous heights is ideal to better characterize the wind resource and reduce project risk. Offshore WindCube can be used with a buoy integration (fixed feet for easy integration, more locks) and is suitable for harsh marine conditions [3].

Figure 1. Galata platform

Fig.2 Windcube mounted on platform

The dust can affected the wiper system of WindCube (Fig. 3)[3].

Fig.3 The wiper system of Windcube

II. TEHNICAL CHARACTERISTICS

The wind cube emits 5 laser beams of light (Fig.4), 4 of which at 28° angle that can be adjusted with the 4 geographical coordinates and one vertical beam that can measure the ascending and descending currents. The aerosols backscatter the laser beam back to the cube [3] which is able to determine the magnitude and direction of the wind. The wind cube was adjusted to measure 20 different levels of altitude

simultaneously. These levels are at 65 m, 70 m, 75 m, 80 m ... up to 175 m.

Fig. 4. Windcube characteristics

An offshore wind turbine is either with fixed monopile foundation [4, 5] or with buoy [6, 7]. Its height, weight, blade length is determined by weather conditions, wind, wave and current characteristics. In Black Sea region is recommended to have an anchored buoy with 4 pylons [8] (Fig. 5) wind turbine mainly due to the depth of water that is bigger than 30m.

Fig.5 Wind turbine with 4 pylons

According to our settings the wind turbine should not be taller than 175 m with blade is zenith direction (Fig. 6).

The dimensions of wind turbine are presented in Fig.7 [8].

Fig.6 Wind turbine with buoy

Elements	Dimension	unit
Hub height	140	mSWL
Interface level	13.5	mSWL
Draft	15	mSWL
Masts diameter	4.5	m
Total length	75	m
Total width	72	m
Columns diameter	9	m
Pontoons dimensions	7.8x5.4	m
Pontoons elevation	-12.3	mSWL
Gangways diameter	3	m
Gangways elevation	12	mSWL

Fig.7 Wind turbine dimensions

The main goal is to improve design and manufacturing brake down structure.

III. DATA AND ANALYSIS

The Windcube exported an “.xml” file every day. Since the installation of the Windcube we have access only for a 186 files, from 30th November up to 7th June. In the file we have different characteristics of the parameters on each of the 20 levels: velocity on 5 direction, temperature and radial wind speed dispersion. These parameters were measured at an interval of 10 seconds. The interval was selected to measure the small variations of gust wind. The file contains 184 columns and 6238 lines. A typical part of the measured parameters is presented in Table 1, for altitude of 65 m.

TABLE I. THE MEASURED PARAMETERS

Time-stamp [hh:mm:ss]	Posit ion	Temperature [K]	Wind speed [m/s]	Wind speed dispersion [%]
12:00:10	V	290.65	-0.95	0.02
12:00:11	0	290.65	2.82	0.02
12:00:12	90	290.65	-4.13	0.02
12:00:13	180	290.65	-11.59	0.02
12:00:14	270	290.65	3.13	0.02

A procedure was written in Macro/Excel to count how many positive/negative wind directions are. The procedure was repeated for files available and then a radial graphic was plotted to see the frequency of the wind (Fig. 8).

Fig.8. Frequency of wind direction

Elements	Mass [te]
Masts	911
Columns	535
Gangways	367
Pontoons	1005
Total floater	1907
Mass per MW	127

IV. CONCLUSION

Mounting the monitoring sistem WindCube Offshore on the existing "Galata" Oil Platform situated close the future wind turbine location, offer the possibility to obtain bankable data for the future WT. The 20 height levels for measurements were chose for a specific 5MW turbine. Rawdata can be collected from system internal HDD, every time the technician reach the platform, but not more often than 2 months; continous power is supplied by the Galata Oil Platform Diesel Generator. Platform offer also a good fixed position for the WindCube, which increases its accuracy. Maintenance is resumed at filling the 40 liter tank with washing fluid.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was performed during implementation of the project BLOW (Black sea floating Offshore Wind) which purpose is to harness the Black Sea's floating offshore wind energy potential. Project BLOW expands on a period of 5 years (2023 - 2027).

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